

Effects of fat and coffee concentration on aroma compounds and their intensity in formulated iced-coffee beverages

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Abstract

Nine iced-coffee beverages were formulated: low fat - low coffee (LF-LC); medium fat - low coffee (MF-LC); high fat - low coffee (HF-LC); low fat - medium coffee (LF-MC); medium fat - medium coffee (MF-MC); high fat - medium coffee (HF-MC); low fat - high coffee (LF-HC); medium fat - high coffee (MF-HC); and high fat - high coffee (HF-HC). Aroma compounds were extracted by Head Space Solid Phase Micro-Extraction (HS-SPME) and analysed by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry Olfactometry (GC-MSO) using Modified Frequency (MF) approach. Fifty-two aroma compounds were detected including one acid, two alcohols, five aldehydes, one aromatic hydrocarbon, two bases, one ester, five furans, four phenols, eight pyrazines, two pyrroles, eight ketones, five sulphurs, and eight others. Five compounds namely '2, 3-butanedione' '2, 5-dimethyl pyrazine' 'furfuryl methyl sulphide' '2-methoxyphenol' and '2, 3-diethyl-5-methyl pyrazine' were commonly identified in all samples. Thirty-one aroma-compounds (MF % = ≥ 50) were considered as important aroma-active compounds. The total number of aroma compounds and their intensity were affected by fat and coffee concentration. For example, the number of aroma compounds and intensity (sum of modified frequency MF values) for LF-HC were 42 and 2292 while it was 13 and 470 for HF-LC, respectively.

Keywords: iced-coffee beverages, HS-SPME, GC-MSO, aroma

Introduction

The aroma or aroma active compounds of coffee are important for coffee flavour and quality coffee beverages. The effect of coffee variety, growing conditions (e.g., altitude, climate, soil type, topography), farming practice, processing, roasting, grinding, and brewing (e.g., water and coffee ratio) on coffee aroma and flavour are well investigated. However, there is very limited published research on iced-coffee beverages aroma profile, and there is no published research showing the effect of fat and coffee interaction on iced-coffee aroma.

Iced-coffee is a type of coffee beverage served chilled. Iced-coffee can be cold brew or normal brewed (hot) prior to adding the coffee into cold milk. Iced-coffee can be formulated with instant coffee using milk and/or fat. Studying iced-coffee has important implications for the beverage industry. The diversification of coffee drinkers and the popularity of "café culture" has brought iced-coffee to the centre stage of the global market. According to the Fortune Business Insights 2020 [1], the global iced coffee beverages market will reach a valuation of US\$ 42.36 billion by the end of 2027. Therefore, global brands are eyeing this lucrative space and trying to develop and launch premium ready to drink coffee which not only fetch higher margins but also provide a more connecting and enchanting coffee-drinking experience [1].

The addition of fat to coffee will have effects on aroma profile and their intensity. For example, the perceived aroma quality of coffee will change with fat concentration. Further, the release of lipophilic compounds decreases with the increase of fat content [2, 3]. Therefore, the aim of this study was to understand the combined effects of varying concentration of fat and coffee on iced-coffee beverages aroma profile and their intensity.

Experimental

Iced-coffee beverages formulation

Nine iced-coffee beverages were formulated with varying fat and coffee concentrations (Table 1). A constant amount (5 g/100mL) of sucrose (100 % crystal cane sugar, CSR, Australia) was added to all the samples. In brief, components for all iced-coffees were added together and homogenized at 5500 rpm (Silverson L4RT-A homogenizer, Triad Scientific, U.S.) for 10 min. The samples were prepared on the same day and stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C until used for extraction and instrumental analysis.

Extraction of volatile compounds

Head-Space Solid-Phase Micro-Extraction (HS-SPME) was used for the extraction of volatile compounds. Three phases (DVB/CAR/PDMS, grey, 50/30 μ m, Merck, North Ryde, Australia) SPME fibres were considered for the extraction of volatile compounds. From formulated iced-coffee, 5 mL of aliquot was taken into 20 mL headspace

vial and sealed with 18 mm Teflon lined magnetic cap (Agilent, Mulgrave, Australia). SPME fibre was exposed to the headspace of the glass vial for 30 min at 35 °C for 20 min. After the extraction process the fibre was injected into the GC inlet for desorption for 5 min at 250 °C, followed by oven temperature program described in the below section.

Table 1: Iced-coffee beverages formulation.

Sample	Cream (g/100 mL)	Coffee (g/100 mL)	Total fat from cream (approx.) (g/100 mL)
LF-HC	0	6.00	0.00
MF-HC	10.50	6.00	3.70
HF-HC	21.20	6.00	7.40
LF-MC	0.00	2.00	0.00
MF-MC	10.50	2.00	3.70
HF-MC	21.20	2.00	7.40
LF-LC	0.00	0.66	0.00
MF-LC	10.50	0.66	3.70
HF-LC	21.20	0.66	7.40

Note: The volume was adjusted by adding skim milk (Devondale, Murray Goulburn Co-operative Co. Ltd, Australia) to make up the volume to 100 mL (Coffee: Nescafé blend 43, Nestlé, Australia; Cream: Bulla thickened cream, Bulla Dairy Foods Pty. Ltd., Australia). LF-LC = low fat - low coffee; MF-LC = medium fat - low coffee; HF-LC = high fat - low coffee; LF-MC = low fat - medium coffee; MF-MC = medium fat -medium coffee; HF-MC = high fat - medium coffee; LF-HC = low fat - high coffee; MF-HC = medium fat - high coffee; and HF-HC = high fat - high coffee.

Analysis of volatile compounds

The analysis was carried out using an Agilent 7890B gas chromatograph equipped with Agilent 7790B Mass Selective Detector (Agilent, Mulgrave, Australia) and Gerstel ODP-3 Olfactory Detector Port (Gerstel, Lasersan Australasia, Tanunda, Australia). The separation was conducted using a BP-5MS, 30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 µm (Trajan Scientific and Medical, Ringwood, Australia) capillary column. A splitless SPME liner (i.d. 0.75mm, PN. 5190-4048, Agilent, USA) was used in the inlet. The inlet was split/splitless using Merlin Microseal (Merck, North Ryde, Australia), and the injection mode was splitless. The inlet temperature was maintained at 250 °C. Research grade He (99.999%) was used as carrier gas under a constant flow of 1.4 mL/min. The column oven temperature started at 40 °C with a 4 min hold time and increased to 200 °C at a rate of 8.6 °C/min with an 8 min hold time. Total analysis time was 30.6 min. MS conditions were: scan range 35 - 450 m. u., solvent cut time 0 min, electron impact mode at 70 eV, MS source 230 °C and MS quad 150 °C.

For ODP, the column was connected with a splitter and the effluent was split 1:1 into two neutral capillary fused silica columns (1.43 m × 0.10 mm i.d. and 0.57 m × 0.10 mm i.d., respectively, Trajan Scientific and Medical, Australia) leading to the MS detector and sniffing port. The auxiliary temperature was maintained at 250 °C and the makeup gas was nitrogen.

GC-O data collection method

Modified Frequency (MF) method was used for GC-O data collection as proposed by Dravnieks 1985 [4]. A panel composed of six trained sniffers (3 female and 3 male) was used to carry out the analyses. Each sniffer smelt each extract once. Each sniffer carried out one session per day, and each session was around 25 min. Panellists were asked to describe and score the intensity of each aroma compounds while sniffing the effluent from ODP. The computer recorded the retention time and sniffing time of each aroma compounds. The aroma-intensity was evaluated using a 6-point scale (1=very weak, 2=weak, 3=clear, 4=very clear, 5=intense, and 6=very intense).

Retention index

An Alkane solution C7 – C40 (49452 U, Supelco, USA) 1000 µg/mL in hexane was employed to calculate the Linear Retention Index (LRI) of each analyte on the BP-5MS column.

HS-SPME, GC-MS-O performance and Retention Time (RT) stability evaluation

The consistent performance of HS-SPME and GC-MS-O were evaluated by monitoring the total peak area of a Quality Control (QC) sample. The coefficient of variation (CV) of the total peak area of QC sample was 9.4% throughout the study. The stability of RT was monitored by n-alkane. The CV % of n-alkane's RT was 0.008.

Statistics

The Modified Frequency (MF) value of each detected aroma compound was calculated using the below formula:

$$MF (\%) = \sqrt{F (\%) \times I (\%)} \quad (\text{Eq 1})$$

Where F (%) is the detection frequency of an aromatic attribute expressed as a percentage ($\frac{\text{number of detections}}{6} \times 100$ %) and I (%) is the average intensity expressed as a percentage of the maximum intensity ($\frac{\text{sum of intensities from 6 sniffers}}{30} \times 100$ %). MF (%) represents the importance of the aroma compound in a sample. The effects of different level of fat and coffee interaction on total intensity or total MF value of different samples and chemical groups was visualised using Excel 2016.

Results and discussion

A total of fifty-two aroma compounds were detected by GC-O analysis, as shown in Table 2, including 1 acid, 2 alcohols, 5 aldehydes, 1 aromatic hydrocarbon, 2 bases, 1 ester, 5 furans, 4 phenols, 8 pyrazines, 2 pyrroles, 8 ketones, 5 sulphurs, and 8 others. For the sake of confirmation or simplicity, those aroma compounds not reaching a minimum GC-O intensity of 25 % (maximum =100 %) and not perceived by three sniffers (maximum = six sniffers) in any of the nine formulated iced-coffee samples were eliminated and considered as noise. Therefore, the absence of a specific aroma compound in some of the samples means that the MF score didn't reach 25 % and the perceived frequency was below three, it still might occur in the sample but the aroma intensity was under the threshold level for the GC-O panellists [5, 6]. The highest number (n=42) of aroma-compounds were identified in LF-HC and the lowest number (n=13) of aroma-compounds were identified in HF-LC. Five aroma compounds namely Butane-2,3-dione, 2,5-Dimethylpyrazine, 2-(Methylsulfanylmethyl)furan, 2-Methoxyphenol and 2,3-Diethyl-5-methylpyrazine were commonly identified in all nine samples.

Among fifty-two aroma compounds, thirty-one presented the highest aroma activities (MF % \geq 50) such as 2, 3-butanedione, 2-butanone, 2-methylbutanal, 2, 3-pentanedione, 4-methylthiazole, methyl pyrazine, furfural and so on. LF-HC contained highest number of intense aroma compounds (n=25) followed by HF-HC (n=23), LF-MC (n=21), MF-HC (n=19), MF-MC (n=17), HF-MC (n=13), LF-LC (n=10), MF-LC (n=7), and HF-LC (n=2). Previous studies reported that aroma compounds such as 2-methylbutanal, furfural, 2,3-diethyl-5-methyl pyrazine, 2,3-butanedione, 2-methoxyphenol, 2,3-pentanedione, 2-butanone, 1-(2-furanyl)ethanone, ethyl pyrazine and 2-furanmethanol [7-9] are important aroma compounds in roasted or brewed coffee. In the current study, based on MF value, thirty-one compounds can be considered as important compounds that could have potential impact on iced-coffee beverages' aroma. Other compounds may be important for overall iced-coffee flavour, but they are not strongly intense, therefore, less important to the iced-coffee beverage aroma.

The MF value of all aroma compounds and major chemical groups were summarised and presented in Figure 1. Overall, the total intensity (sum of MF values) of each sample and different chemical groups' aroma-intensity were affected by fat and coffee ratio. The changes in intensity can be caused by different factors. For example, fat retains most volatiles, while dairy products also contain protein and carbohydrate that can interact by adsorption, entrapment, and encapsulation [10]. Therefore, a simple correlation between fat level and aroma release cannot be established. However, in all samples, high fat content had more negative impact on aroma intensity compared to the zero fat. Contrary, small effect was observed on aroma intensity between medium and high coffee concentration. The possible reason could be the complex matrices effect of volatiles e.g. low aroma intense compounds suppressed by the high intense compounds [11].

Conclusion

Fat and coffee ratio is important to the volatile aroma compounds release and their intensity. Overall, volatile release and/or the intensity of aroma compounds decreased with the increase of fat concentration while it was opposite with coffee concentration. For example, lower number of aroma compounds identified in low coffee concentration. This study suggested that too low coffee concentration is not ideal for the desirable coffee flavour or to maintain the characteristic coffee flavour. Similarly, too much fat in coffee affects the release of the volatiles and their intensity. Therefore, adding too much fat alter the coffee flavour. We used three different levels of fat and coffee concentration and noticed MF-MC is an appropriate ratio to maintain the characteristic coffee aroma. Future study could narrow the range of fat and coffee around the most liked concentrations used in this study to find out the fine-tuning concentrations to maximise the coffee like flavour and consumer acceptance. The result of this study can be utilised to reformulate the iced-coffee with desirable coffee aroma.

Figure 1: Effects of fat and coffee concentration on the total intensity (sum of MF values) of iced-coffee sample and different chemical groups.

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Table 2: List of aroma compounds and their Modified Frequency (MF) values as detected using GC-MS-O. Important aroma compounds (MF %≥ 50) in relation to flavour.

#	Compounds	Aroma descriptions	LRI ¹ (Cal.)	LRI ² (Ref.)	Chemical group	MF values									Identification method ³
						LF-HC	MF-HC	HF-HC	LF-MC	MF-MC	HF-MC	LF-LC	MF-MC	HF-MC	
1	2-Methylpropan-1-ol	caramel, cocoa, green, malt, nut	-	-	Aldehyde	30	29	26	36	30	0	0	0	0	AD, MS
2	Butane-2,3-dione	butter, caramel, fruit, sweet, yogurt	-	-	Ketone	38	31	51	31	45	38	38	47	26	AD, MS
3	Butan-2-one	ether, fragrant, fruit, pleasant, sweet	-	-	Ketone	59	59	65	47	43	57	0	0	0	AD, MS
4	2-Methylbutanal	acid, almond, cocoa, malt, pungent, fermented	660	654	Aldehyde	66	78	68	78	75	50	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
5	Pentane-2,3-dione	bitter, butter, caramel, fruit, sweet	697	699	Ketone	41	49	59	0	30	29	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
6	2-Methylthiophene	Sulphur	768	771	Sulphur	46	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
7	Methyl 3-methylbutanoate	apple, fruit, pineapple	775	773	Esters	0	0	0	0	36	38	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
8	Hexanal	grass, green	797	801	Aldehyde	41	38	0	45	26	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
9	1-Ethylpyrrole	chemical, roast	809	810	Pyrrole	35	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
10	4-Methyl-1,3-thiazole	green, nut, roasted meat	812	814	Sulphur	57	0	0	57	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
11	2-Methylpyrazine	cocoa, green, hazelnut, popcorn, roasted	819	821	Pyrazine	61	43	45	56	35	45	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
12	Furan-2-carbaldehyde	almond, baked potatoes, bread, candy, floral	828	835	Furan	0	38	59	0	33	31	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
13	2,4,5- Trimethyl-1,3-oxazole	dairy, butter, aged cheeses, yogurt, caramel	844	848	Oxazol(in)es	37	59	78	45	45	26	0	0	29	AD, LRI, MS
14	Furan-2-ylmethanol	burnt, caramel, cooked, solvent	853	854	Furan	65	45	0	61	0	33	55	55	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
15	Heptan-2-ol	citrus, coconut, fried, mushroom, oil	899	899	Alcohol	71	66	70	75	63	51	0	45	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
16	1-(Furan-2-yl) ethenone	cocoa, coffee, smoke, tobacco	904	913	Furan	51	82	85	65	80	78	63	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST

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17	2,5-Dimethylpyrazine	burnt plastic, cocoa, medicine, nutty	907	914	Pyrazine	65	78	90	80	82	80	35	78	29	AD, LRI, MS, ST
18	2-Ethylpyrazine	green, iron scorch, must, peanut butter, roasted	911	915	Pyrazine	65	59	68	47	65	59	0	31	38	AD, LRI, MS, ST
19	5-Methylfuran-2-carbaldehyde	almond, caramel, cooked, roasted garlic, spice	957	961	Furan	53	33	45	57	57	33	0	0	26	AD, LRI, MS
20	(Methyltrisulfanyl)methane	cabbage, fish, onion, sulphur, sweat	968	968	Sulphur	75	36	38	71	55	55	53	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
21	Phenol	medicine, phenol, sharp, smoke, spice	978	984	Phenol	0	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
22	Furan-2-ylmethyl acetate	roast, fruity, sweet	988	990	Furan	43	26	33	31	43	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
23	2-Ethyl-6-methylpyrazine	green, nut, roasted	994	997	Pyrazine	39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
24	2-(Methylsulfanylmethyl) furan	coffee	996	995	Sulphur	76	73	82	63	78	71	57	38	38	AD, LRI, MS
25	2-Ethyl-3-methylpyrazine	green, must, nut, potato, roasted	998	999	Pyrazine	65	63	76	45	73	35	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
26	3-Methylcyclopentane-1,2-dione	coffee, burnt, sugar	1030	1030	Ketone	55	60	76	69	47	0	35	57	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
27	2-Phenylacetaldehyde	pungent, fermented, earthy	1037	1038	Aldehyde	53	53	53	66	54	59	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
28	1-Ethylpyrrole-2-carbaldehyde	burnt, roasted, smoky	1045	1046	Bases	65	75	68	55	35	35	48	33	0	AD, LRI, MS
29	1-(1H-pyrrol-2-yl) ethenone	bread, cocoa, hazelnut, walnut	1059	1063	Ketone	53	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
30	Unknown	musty, bread	1062	-	-	41	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
31	3-Ethyl-2,5-dimethylpyrazine	broth, earth, potato, roast	1076	1079	Pyrazine	47	75	83	76	67	55	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
32	2-Methoxyphenol	bacon, medicine, phenol, smoke, wood, vanilla	1084	1089	Phenol	68	78	58	61	47	65	66	78	61	AD, LRI, MS
33	Nonan-2-one	pleasant, hot milk, fragrant, fruit, green	1087	1090	Ketone	71	78	82	68	51	47	83	53	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
34	Unknown	cereal, nutty, musty, roasted	1088	-	-	59	49	59	37	35	49	0	0	0	

35	Nonanal	citrus, fat, green, paint, pungent	1101	1104	Aldehyde	0	65	54	57	63	51	0	38	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
36	Unknown	roast, earth, garden	1128	-	-	0	43	37	0	41	0	0	0	0	-
37	2,3-Diethyl-5-methylpyrazine	earth, meat, potato, roast	1149	1151	Pyrazine	73	69	53	60	67	41	78	71	67	AD, LRI, MS, ST
38	3,5-Diethyl-2-methylpyrazine	baked, cocoa, roast, rum, sweet	1153	1155	Pyrazine	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
39	Octanoic acid	fat, cheese, rancid	1171	1174	Acid	73	54	63	76	57	29	80	76	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
40	1-(Furan-2-ylmethyl) pyrrole	cocoa, green, roast	1176	1182	Pyrrole	82	62	51	69	56	71	87	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
41	2-[(Methylsulfonyl)methyl] furan	Smoke	1213	1222	Sulphur	73	41	39	71	53	31	71	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
42	Unknown	cocoa, green, mint	1239	-	-	0	39	0	0	26	29	0	33	0	-
43	4-Ethyl-2-methoxyphenol	medicine, smoke, woody	1274	1282	Phenol	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS, ST
44	Undecan-2-one	fatty, cheese, butter, nut, fruit, floral	1289	1295	Ketone	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
45	4-Ethenyl-2-methoxyphenol	clove, curry, smoke, spice	1309	1317	Phenol	37	45	45	35	45	0	0	0	31	AD, LRI, MS, ST
46	Unknown	roasted, smoke, nutty	1333	-	-	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
47	Unknown	dairy, milky, cheese, pleasant	1345	-	-	0	37	0	0	0	0	0	29	31	-
48	1-(2,6,6-Trimethylcyclohexa-1,3-dien-1-yl) but-2-en-1-one	boiled apple, floral, fruit, grape, tea	1385	1388	Ketone	60	48	0	55	43	29	0	0	0	AD, LRI, MS
49	Unknown	roast, smoky	1453	-	-	46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-
50	3,3,7-Trimethyl-8-methylidenetricyclo [5.4.0.0 ^{2,9}] undecane	sweet, woody, rose, vegetable, flower	1461	1451	Aromatic Hydrocarbon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	35	AD, LRI, MS
51	Dodecan-1-ol	fat, wax	1475	1473	Alcohol	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	29	AD, LRI, MS, ST
52	Unknown	fruity, sweet	1596	-	-	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	36	-

Note: ¹ LRI in BP-5MS column; ² LRI in DB-5MS column; ³ Identification method: MS = matching mass spectra of GC-MS analysis with those from the NIST 2017 library (library match: ≥ 70 %); AD = coincidence of Aroma Description (AD) reported in online data base (<http://www.odour.org.uk>; <http://flavornet.org>; and <http://www.thegoodscentscompany.com/>) or literature; LRI = coincidence of Linear Retention Index (LRI) reported in online data base (e.g. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/> and <https://www.pherobase.com/>) or literature; ST = coincidence of LRI with authentic standard.